

Selective CRM recovery from acidic solutions by nanofiltration

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Introduction

The recovery of resources from waste streams is becoming more and more important. Industries are aiming increasingly at zero-liquid-discharge and circular economy solutions. Nanofiltration (NF) is a well-known separation technique and applied in many sectors such as food and pharma industry. Recently, NF has become attractive for resource recovery applications. For instance, studies have shown that NF is a suitable technology for phosphorus recovery from sewage sludge [1]. Acid resistant membranes, however, in combination with further purification steps (e.g. precipitation, liquid-liquid extraction, sorption) offer options for selective recovery of critical raw materials from complex

Figure 1: Schematic process scheme of combining acid resistant NF with pre-/post-treatment for selective

secondary sources (Figure 1). The particular advantage of NF lies in the selectivity towards monovalent and multivalent ions. Previously, we demonstrated that acid resistant NF combined with liquid-liquid extraction allows an effective recovery of indium (95%) from photovoltaic cell (CIGS) leachates [2]. In this study the application of NF was expanded to the recovery of CRM (in particular Scandium) for large scale applications on promising complex waste streams. In addition to commercially available membranes, layer-by-layer (LbL) modified membranes were tested for scandium recovery. LbL-modification can be used for tailoring the filtration properties of NF [3]. A systematic study on the combined use of (LbL)-NF with different pre-/post-treatment steps was conducted and initial recommendations on the use of acid resistant NF for the selective and efficient recovery of CRM from secondary sources derived.

Methods

For LbL modification, capillary ultrafiltration membranes provided by Pentair were coated with polyelectrolytes (polydiallyldimethylammonium chloride/polysodiumstyrenesulfonate).

In this case 5 bi-layers were chosen. As a benchmark, a commercially available membrane (Duracid, General Electric, Fairfield, USA) was used. Filtration experiments were carried out using a 1M HCl solution containing 90mg/L scandium and 1'500 mg/L iron. As a pretreatment, the pH was adjusted to pH=1.5. Iron and scandium retention was determined using ICP-OES.

Results and Conclusion

During the experimental time, the retention efficiencies for both Iron and Scandium remained almost constant over time and both membranes (Figure 2). This indicates

Figure 2: Scandium and iron retention for LbL and Duracid membrane in 1 M HCl

that both membranes were acid resistant. Noticeably, a low (<10%) iron retention for both the Duracid and the LbL-membrane was achieved, hence iron was not concentrated in the retentate. The scandium retention for the LbL membrane was indeed higher (70%) compared to the commercially available Duracid membrane (30%), resulting in a scandium enriched retentate (+40%) using LbL membranes in contrast to commercially available membranes. These results show the considerable potential for acid resistant NF in general and LbL modified NF in particular for many difficult (complex) separation processes. Due to their unique

properties and high resistance towards a harsh acidic environment LbL membranes can be used to recover CRM from diverse of waste streams.

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